

SoM

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6.1. Power supplies

	Min	Typical	Max	Unit
Main Power Supply, DC-IN	3.3	3.7	4.5	V

6.2. Power Consumption

CPU usage:

Task	SOM VBAT current draw in ma @3.7v
Suspend	8mA
Idle (~10% CPU) @ 400mhz	220mA
FHD Video playback	430mA
100% CPU Dhrystone test – Dual core	510mA
100% CPU Dhrystone test – Quad core	760mA

Additional peripherals:

Task	SOM VBAT current draw in ma @3.7v
WLAN transmission 2.4Ghz 802.11(b/g/n)	~(350-430)mA
WLAN transmission 5Ghz 802.11(a)	~440

Output power rails:

Power Rail	Max allowed current draw in ma
SW4_1V8	200mA
GEN_2V5	200mA

8. Environmental Specifications

	Min	Max
Commercial Operating Temperature Range	0 °C	+70 °C
Extended Operating Temperature Range	-20 °C	+85 °C
Industrial Operating Temperature Range	-40°C	+85 °C
Referring MIL-HDBK-217F-2 Parts Count Reliability Prediction Method Model:		
50Deg Celsius, Class B-1, GM	121 Khrs >	
50Deg Celsius, Class B-1, GB	1400 Khrs >	
Shock Resistance	50G/20 ms	
Vibration	20G/0 - 600 Hz	